

Estimating the optimal exchange rate using the probabilistic market model toolkit

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Аннотация. В условиях глобализации мировой экономической системы в России отмечались значительные колебания курса национальной валюты как в сторону ослабления, так и в сторону укрепления. Это обстоятельство породило дискуссии практиков и теоретиков о целесообразности поиска оптимального курса рубля и мерах по его поддержке в условиях санкционных ограничений. Однако, эти дискуссии не базировались ни на модельных, ни на экспериментальных оценках, поскольку их просто не было. Авторами предпринята попытка восполнить этот пробел. Для этого предложено использовать вероятностную модель рынка в двух-отраслевом приближении. На примере двух идентичных стран типа России был проведен виртуальный эксперимент по их конкурентному объединению в двух-страновую модель условно «единого мирового рынка». Причем отличие этих стран заключается в регулировании валютного курса и ресурсной обеспеченности. Цифровые эксперименты, проведенные в рамках объединенной вероятностной модели рынка, показали достаточно убедительные зависимости относительно успешности стран. Наложение на этот фактор динамики укрепления (ослабления) курса рубля для стран с разной ресурсной обеспеченностью позволило получить разные модели, которые вполне пригодны для формирования рекомендаций по оптимальному регулированию курса рубля.

Abstract. In the context of globalization of the world economic system, significant fluctuations in the national currency exchange rate, both weakening and strengthening, were observed in Russia. This circumstance gave rise to discussions among practitioners and theorists about the advisability of finding the optimal ruble exchange rate and measures to support it in the context of sanctions. However, these discussions were not based on either model or experimental estimates, since they simply did not exist. The authors attempted to fill this gap. For this purpose, it was proposed to use a probabilistic market model in a two-industry approximation. Using the example of two identical countries such as Russia, a virtual experiment was conducted on their competitive unification into a two-country model of a conditionally "single world market". Moreover, the difference between these countries lies in the regulation of the exchange rate and resource endowment. Digital experiments conducted within the framework of the combined probabilistic market model showed quite convincing dependencies on the relative success of countries. Superimposing on this factor the dynamics of strengthening (weakening) of the ruble exchange rate for countries with different resource endowments made it possible to obtain different models that are quite suitable for forming recommendations for optimal regulation of the ruble exchange rate.

Ключевые слова: глобальная экономическая система, вероятностная модель рынка, курс национальной валюты, поиск оптимального курса рубля.

Keywords: global economic system, probabilistic market model, national currency exchange rate, search for the optimal ruble exchange rate.

Introduction

In the modern world, the exchange rate is a significant instrument in the economic policy of the state. It is subject to the influence of market factors and for this reason can change. The choice of the exchange rate regime in a fixed or floating position depends on the domestic economic situation, the state of money circulation, the balance of payments, the role of the state in the world economy and international trade, accumulated gold and foreign exchange reserves. The state determines the exchange rate regime and strives to optimize it in order to reduce the impact of global market factors on the national economy, minimize inflationary expectations, increase the

regulatory role of exchange rates and actively participate in global economic relations.

Conducting an effective policy in the currency sphere as one of the main components of the economic system is of fundamental importance in the conditions of the formation of global financial markets. The challenges of globalization sharply increase the vulnerability of the national economy to external shocks and require appropriate mechanisms to ensure the adaptation of the financial system to changes in the cross-border movement of capital. Accordingly, a flexible currency policy is a necessary condition for increasing Russia's competitiveness, its

active participation in the global economy and interaction, first of all, with friendly countries.

The relevance of the chosen topic is that the exchange rate has a significant impact on the country's foreign trade, since the competitiveness of its goods on world markets largely depends on its level. The exchange rate affects the direction of international capital flows. The decision to invest national capital in the assets of a particular country is made based on the expected real return on invested capital, which depends on the interest rate and expected changes in the exchange rate.

The currency of each country receives its assessment on the international financial market based on various factors. The exchange rate is formed in relation to the currency of another country, which characterizes the equivalence of currency exchange. It is also used in financial transactions between commercial banks and the population, but the sale and purchase rates differ due to the need to compensate for the services of the bank as an intermediary. It should be noted that many components of the economy depend on the exchange rate. The national currency rate affects prices in domestic consumer markets, the standard of living of the population, the volume of export and import transactions, and, consequently, the balance of payments, the level of

inflation in the country, as well as the revenues of the state budget.

Materials and methods

Using Russia as an example, it can be noted that setting the ruble exchange rate today is a flexible instrument of economic policy. It takes into account a set of multidirectional factors, such as changes in import and export prices, sentiments and expectations of investors in Russia and the world, changes in the monetary policy of the Central Bank of Russia and other countries. Factors influencing the exchange rate are divided into structural (acting in the long term) and market factors (causing short-term fluctuations in the exchange rate). Structural factors include the competitiveness of a country's goods on the world market and its change, the state of the balance of payments of the state, the purchasing power of the currency and the rate of inflation, the difference in interest rates in different countries, government regulation of the exchange rate, the degree of openness of the economy. Market factors include the activity of currency markets, speculative currency transactions, forecasts, the cyclicity of business activity in the country, crises, wars, natural disasters, etc. [1]. Thus, due to external and internal market and political factors, the exchange rate of the Russian ruble was subject to significant changes. Its fluctuations over the last three years are reflected in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the ruble to US dollar exchange rate for the period 31.12.2021 – 27.12.2024 rr.
Source: <https://www.finmarket.ru/currency/rates/?id=10148&pv=1>.

1) The need to take into account sanctions restrictions and countermeasures

The start of the special military operation (SMO) of the Russian Armed Forces in Ukraine became the pretext for the unleashing of large-scale sanctions pressure on Russia by the countries of the collective West. The United States, Great Britain and most EU member states, with the exception of Hungary and Slovakia, were particularly successful in this. On December 16, 2024, the EU Council adopted the fifteenth package of sanctions [2]. The focus of the restrictions included in it is aimed at combating the Russian shadow fleet, as well as countering the circumvention of sanctions. This package also included one of the country's largest microelectronics companies, the Silicon EL Group. It also included 32 more companies that were allegedly involved in the

supply of dual-use goods and technologies to Russia. Some of them are located in third countries, including China, India, Iran, Serbia and the United Arab Emirates.

In total, more than 15 thousand sanctions have been imposed against Russia since the beginning of 2022, which is a world record. The United States has applied the largest number of anti-Russian sanctions - more than 3.5 thousand restrictive measures. Switzerland is second - 2,377 sanctions. Canada is third with 2,087 restrictions. Over a thousand sanctions against the Russian Federation were also imposed by: Great Britain (1949), the European Union (1837), New Zealand (1620) and Australia (1254) [2]. Through sanctions pressure, the United States, Great Britain and EU member states intended to suppress the development of our country's

economy and oust it from the ranks of world leaders. Sanction restrictions affected many sectors of the Russian economy - from high-tech imports to luxury goods.

The actions of the Russian authorities in the context of sanctions pressure can be generally divided into counter-sanctions measures, which involve causing damage to the countries that imposed sanctions, and measures to overcome the consequences of sanctions for the domestic economy. The former mainly involved mirror measures, in particular the closure of airspace (February 28, 2022), the cessation of supplies of RD-180 rocket engines to the United States (March 3, 2022), the transfer of payments for the purchase and leasing of foreign aircraft to rubles (April 1, 2022), the transfer of payments for the supply of Russian gas to rubles (May 23, 2022), the cessation of gas supplies to Poland and Bulgaria, then to Finland, the Netherlands, Denmark, the legalization of parallel imports (March 29, 2022), the introduction of temporary bans on the export of wheat, rye, barley and corn (March 14, 2022), as well as sanctions against certain foreign individuals and legal entities, etc. [3].

In Russia, the introduction of measures to counter sanctions restrictions was quite predictable.

Firstly, the freezing of the Russian Federation's gold and foreign exchange reserves, the ban on the use of dollars and euros in trade settlements became a tangible blow to the Russian financial system. However, thanks to the advance preparation of the Central Bank of Russia for such a scenario, only half of the assets denominated in dollars and euros were frozen.

Secondly, an important goal of the sanctions policy of the United States, Great Britain and the EU countries was the collapse of the ruble. Indeed, the introduced restrictions on the ruble exchange rate initially worked. However, the adoption of tough measures by the Central Bank of Russia made it possible to stabilize the situation through: a sharp increase in the key rate to 20%, the introduction of requirements for exporters to sell 80% of foreign exchange earnings, and restrictions for individuals on the sale of currency on the domestic market. This led to the strengthening of the ruble exchange rate. Thus, already at the end of March 2022, the ruble exchange rate began to strengthen significantly. And at the end of May, it returned to a comfortable range of 75-80 rubles per dollar. However, this ratio became quite dangerous for the further development of the Russian economy. Therefore, in June 2022, the ruble exchange rate was adjusted, and by the end of this month it was 54-64 rubles per dollar. The ruble responded to each sanction restriction with a short-term decline, and then returned to its usual range.

The decree signed by the President of Russia that due to the loss of trust in unfriendly countries, from April 1, 2022, they must pay for gas supplied from the Russian Federation in rubles, and not in dollars and euros, contributed to a serious strengthening of the ruble. This retaliatory step had a negative impact on the economy of the EU countries. For a

number of reasons, they were not ready to function when making payments for energy supplies in rubles. The Russian financial system turned out to be much more stable than Western politicians imagined. And the competent measures of the Central Bank helped to neutralize the blow inflicted by the sanctions. To reduce dependence on foreign financial services, an analogue of the international SWIFT system was developed in Russia - SPFS (financial message transfer system), the Mir payment system was launched, and the transition to National credit ratings was carried out.

At the same time, the reorientation of trade flows to friendly CIS and Asian countries began, along with declared goals for import substitution, mainly in sectors such as agriculture, mechanical engineering, IT technologies and government procurement. Nevertheless, the dependence of Russian production on imported components in certain sectors remains quite high by the end of 2024.

In general, one of the long-term priorities in countering sanctions should be international finance. This means moving away from the use of the US dollar in international settlements not only by Russia, but also by other partner countries. The second priority is trade diversification, both in terms of imports and exports. At the same time, it is important that Russia does not close all trade flows to a single major partner, such as China. The third priority is commitment to and upholding in the UN Security Council the supremacy of international law, which does not allow the introduction of unilateral sanctions that violate human rights in the country against which these sanctions were introduced. Finally, the fourth priority is the development of domestic production and new technologies that will allow replacing foreign analogues.

In 2024, the US imposed sanctions on the Russian financial sector, which significantly changed the landscape of the foreign exchange market. On June 12, the US authorities imposed blocking sanctions against the Moscow Exchange Group, which led to a halt in exchange trading in the US dollar, euro and Hong Kong dollar. After that, the Central Bank of Russia began to set the official exchange rates of these currencies to the ruble based on bank reports on transactions in the over-the-counter foreign exchange market. However, as a result of the imposed restrictions, as well as under the influence of export-import flows, the dollar exchange rate began to rise steadily and on November 29, 2022, it reached an absolute mark of 109.5782 rubles per US dollar (the maximum since mid-March 2022). A week earlier, large-scale blocking sanctions were imposed by the US against the Russian financial sector in relation to more than 50 Russian banks with international ties, including Gazprombank, which was an important link in the payment of European countries for Russian gas supplies. Against this backdrop, the Bank of Russia took measures to stabilize the foreign exchange market, refusing to purchase currency under the budget rule until the end of 2024. They led to a decrease in panic among players and stabilization of

the exchange rate near the 100 ruble per US dollar mark [4].

2) Assessing the consequences of the introduction of sanctions restrictions for Western countries

Gradually, many countries that actively introduced sanctions against Russia were surprised to find that they themselves faced serious economic problems due to anti-Russian restrictions. Moreover, in a variety of areas [5]. An important consequence of the sanctions policy towards Russia was the energy problems in European countries due to their refusal of Russian energy resources. Anti-Russian sanctions led to energy prices rising. The consequences for European economies were more significant than for the United States, since they are less dependent on Russian energy resources. Gas, fuel and other oil products in the European Union have become many times more expensive. As a result, Western European countries are on the brink of crisis. At the same time, the services of new suppliers for European countries are now more expensive. However, the significance of the energy resource factor varies significantly for different countries. Thus, for Eastern European countries, it is extremely difficult to replace Russian gas and oil with alternative suppliers.

As a result of the introduction of ill-considered sanctions against Russia, the EU financial system became unbalanced. At the same time, anti-Russian sanctions were superimposed on the consequences of coronavirus restrictions. The consequence of this was the shutdown of enterprises, bankruptcy of companies and an increase in prices for consumers. First of all, they affected the most sensitive group of goods, namely: food and motor fuel.

According to the US Department of Energy, in the first quarter of 2022 alone, gasoline prices in the US rose by almost 30% to \$1.12 per liter. At the same time, according to Eurostat calculations, at gas stations in Germany, a liter of fuel rose in price by 29% (to \$2.38 per liter), in France - by 21% (to \$2.19 per liter), in Italy - by 24% (to \$2.37 per liter), and in the Netherlands - by 17% (to \$2.54 per liter) [5].

The European Metals Trade Association noted that half of Europe's aluminum and zinc production had been halted. Europe's largest steelmaker Arcelor Mittal has idled blast furnaces in Germany. One of the world's top aluminum producers, Alcoa, is cutting production at its smelter in Norway by a third. And the world's largest zinc producer, Nyrstar, is suspending production in the Netherlands until "further notice."

As a result, a number of manufacturing companies in Europe have been forced to reduce production and staff numbers, and some of the largest European companies are moving their production from Europe to the United States. In particular, Volkswagen AG announced an increase in investment in production facilities in the United States. At the same time, the United States is pursuing a policy to stimulate industrialization and reduce inflation,

which increases the country's attractiveness for European business.

Due to rising costs of fertilizer production, the profitability of the agricultural sector is under great pressure. Many foreign and Russian experts believe that a food crisis in some European countries is quite possible.

Anti-Russian restrictions have seriously affected ordinary consumers in the US and Europe. The current socio-economic situation in Europe is characterized by rising inflation and a decline in production, people's discontent reaching the point of strikes, and a significant increase in prices for food and utilities. Electricity, light, and heating bills have soared by 50-300%.

The sharp rise in energy prices has resulted in a rise in the price of a number of other goods in the US and Europe. Inflation in the European Union began to rise at the beginning of 2021, exceeded the target in the summer, jumped even more after the introduction of large-scale sanctions against Russia and reached a peak in October 2022 - 10.6%. Moreover, inflation in the energy sector reached 41.5%, which led to food inflation. Since then, the inflation rate in Europe has been falling, energy inflation has not only stabilized, but also turned negative: minus 6.3% in January 2024. The overall inflation rate in January was 2.8% [6].

Trust in the settlement system has also decreased. According to Russian President V.V. Putin, "The collective West has effectively drawn a line under the reliability of its currencies, crossed out trust in these currencies. Both the US and the EU have declared, in principle, a real default on their obligations to Russia. And now everyone in the world knows that obligations in dollars and euros may not be fulfilled" [7].

In addition, logistics suffered. The implementation of the SVO in Ukraine created new problems for the global supply chains of raw materials and goods disrupted by the pandemic. International corporations from the USA, India, Germany and other countries, which had previously launched production in Ukraine and bought the country's production assets, suffered losses. Automobile plants in Germany, which were dependent on Ukrainian component manufacturers, are no longer operating, supplies for the steel industry to various countries as far away as Japan have been reduced. Air, sea and land supply routes through Ukraine have been interrupted. The conflict also limited the huge export of goods from Russia and Ukraine, leading to higher prices for oil, natural gas, wheat and sunflower oil. According to Commerzbank AG, Russia and Ukraine account for a third of the world's wheat exports, 19% of corn and 80% of sunflower oil. The US freight forwarding company Flexport announced that it had stopped accepting orders for cargo flights from Asia to Europe via Russia. Now planes are choosing a longer route over the Middle East [8].

3) Justification of the methodology used

To regulate and forecast the optimal ruble exchange rate taking into account the impact of the

SVO on the Russian and global economy, it seems relevant to use probabilistic models of hybrid economic systems. With their help, one can obtain estimates close to real ones of the impact of changes in the parameters of the economic system on economic growth and incomes of agents. For fundamental and practical reasons, the exchange rate of the national currency, which has shown a large range of fluctuations ($\pm 50\%$), is of primary interest. In this regard, the dynamics of the ruble exchange rate is of great importance for Russia's economic growth, and regulation of the ruble exchange rate has now become a key instrument of economic policy.

The weakening of the ruble by -50% was perceived as a catastrophe. It caused a whole series of significant (selling gas for rubles) and insignificant (increasing the key rate to 25%) measures. Against the backdrop of a growing influx of hydrocarbon dollars, these measures led to a sharp strengthening of the ruble by about the same 50%.

According to the world's largest financial news agency Bloomberg, the ruble was named the best currency of 2022 in the world [9]. In Russia, the strengthening of the ruble was initially assessed as a positive phenomenon. However, already in April-May 2022, at working meetings, industrialists began to express concern about the obvious decrease in the competitiveness of their products in relation to external players.

After this, the Russian government took measures aimed at preventing excessive strengthening of the ruble exchange rate. However, in practice, these measures do not look systemic, and from the outside they look more like throwing from side to side using the "trial and error" method beloved by physicists. From our point of view, this is due to the absence of any models that would allow at least a

general estimate of the optimal ruble exchange rate in statics and dynamics. In this paper, an attempt is made to fill this gap using a probabilistic model of hybrid economic systems in a two-subsystem version [10], [11].

Given the complexity of this multifactorial task, the level of our claims in constructing the first model is reduced to assessing the most general trends in the weakening or strengthening of the ruble exchange rate. For this purpose, we carried out a virtual experiment to unite two absolutely identical countries into a "single world market". One of them operates under conditions of an equilibrium ruble exchange rate, and the second strengthens (or weakens) the national currency (ruble). Since the economy of both countries within the model functions without export and import duties, a single system for assessing the market value of goods should be formed, the nature of which in the "money-goods-money" system is irrelevant. At the same time, in order not to deviate from real life on the main factor for Russia, we assume that these countries may have different resource endowments and separate access to their own and foreign resources.

Results and discussion

For this model problem, a basic probabilistic model can be applied, which we have often considered in a two-industry version [12], [13]. However, the role of industries here will be played by entire countries. Despite the general averaging in assessing market values for agents and goods, we will assume separate accounting of available and used natural resources. Then the probabilistic model of the development of these two countries united in the world market in a form convenient for programming will have the form:

$$A(i+1) = A(i) - SA(i)^* \times A(i) + \langle SA(i) \rangle^* \times A(i) - (\alpha) \times A(i) \quad (1)$$

$$\langle SA(i) \rangle = (A(i)^* SA(i)^t + B(i)^* SB(i)^t + r_{a(i)} \times v_{a(i)}) \times (A(i)^t + B(i)^t + r_{a(i)})^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$$r_{a(i+1)} = r_a - r_{a(i)} \times v_{a(i)} + r_{a(i)} \times \langle SA(i) \rangle \quad (3)$$

$$B(i+1) = B(i) - SB(i)^* \times B(i) + \langle SB(i) \rangle^* \times B(i) \quad (4)$$

$$\langle SB(i) \rangle = (B(i)^* SB(i)^t + A(i)^* SA(i)^t + r_{b(i)} \times v_{b(i)}) \times (B(i)^t + A(i)^t + r_{b(i)})^{-1} \quad (5)$$

$$r_{b(i+1)} = r_{b(i)} - r_{b(i)} \times v_{b(i)} + r_{b(i)} \times \langle SB(i) \rangle \quad (6)$$

where i – years from 0 to N ;
 $A(i)$ – vector of capitals (gross incomes) of country's agents A;
 $r_{a(i)}$ – available for use capitalized natural resources (which may include labor) for a country A;
 $SA(i)$ – vector of relative costs of production agents of the country A;
 $\langle SA(i) \rangle$ – average cost (market value) of the country A;
 $v_{a(i)}$ – resource availability parameter in country A, which has the meaning of the threshold cost of production by an agent who, at a given level of resource availability, has zero profitability.

$B(i)$ – vector of capitals (gross incomes) of country's agents B;
 $r_{b(i)}$ – available for use capitalized natural resources (which may include labor) for a country B;
 $SB(i)$ – vector of relative costs of production agents of the country B;
 $\langle SB(i) \rangle$ – average cost (market value) of the country B;
 $v_{b(i)}$ – resource availability parameter in country B, which has the meaning of the threshold cost of production by an agent who, at a given level of resource availability, has zero profitability.
 I – unit vector;

t – transposition symbol;
 *x – symbol for matrix element-wise multiplication;

$A*B$ – normal matrix multiplication;

$A.*B$ – element-wise matrix multiplication in MATLAB and some other languages.

As zero conditions, we will assume that all parameters of country A and country B are the same. There are 100 agents in each country. Numerous numerical experiments performed earlier show that, given the real level of measurement errors that occur in economies, this is a sufficient initial number [14]. Each agent has a starting capital equal to 1. The relative errors in estimating market values from the most efficient agent of country A to the most inefficient vary in the range $0.01 \div 0.10$, for countries A and B, without a random component.

Accessibility Options $V_a = V_b = 0,09$ under natural conditions will provide approximately 3% annual growth at the start

$$ra = rb = 10 \times A(0)^* \times I^T \quad (7)$$

where I – single factor.

In addition, we will assume that at the start, the equilibrium currencies in countries A and B ensure absolutely identical growth.

In a simplified model, the effect of the strengthening of the ruble in country A is reduced to an increase in the current income of agents (since they receive more goods from country B as a result of the exchange) with a simultaneous deterioration in the relative cost [10]. Given the small effect on the average values, this is reduced to varying the alpha parameter in formula (1).

In a more precise formulation, we must clearly isolate the withdrawn monetized portion of income $\beta_a * A(i)$ and $\beta_b * B(i)$ from the total growth of capitalization ($B(i)$ in the cycle $i \rightarrow i+1$), supplement

formulas (1) and (3) with these terms, and accordingly adjust the parameters V_a and V_b based on the experimentally observed growth rate of ~ 0.03 . This clarification is not formal, but directly follows from the actually observed uncertainty of the change in the value of the non-monetized portion of agents' capital with sudden changes in the ruble exchange rate against the dollar.

Thus, during the falls (strengthenings) of the ruble, which Russia has experienced repeatedly in its recent history, residential and non-residential real estate, power plants, and equipment demonstrated a tendency to maintain dollar prices rather than ruble prices. In this regard, it can be assumed that with a sudden change in the ruble exchange rate by $(1+\alpha)$ times, only the monetized part of the capital change changes proportionally, while the non-monetized part remains unchanged in conditional absolute money. Then the criterion for the current effectiveness of ruble targeting can be the relative income parameter:

$$Z(i) = (1 + \alpha) * (A(i) * I1^T) (B(i) * I1^T)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

And the criterion for the optimality of the exchange rate policy on a 40-year planning horizon can be the indicator $z(i)$ - the average value of relative profitability over these 40 years.

The results of the first digital experiments on managing the ruble exchange rate are presented in Figures 2–5. In all figures, the currency parameter 50 corresponds to the identical ruble exchange rate in country A and in country B. The currency parameter 0 corresponds to the strengthening of the ruble in country A by 50% relative to the equilibrium value maintained in country B.

Fig. 2. The effect of the ruble exchange rate.
 Source: developed by the authors.

The currency parameter of 100 corresponds to a weakening of the ruble in country A by 50%.

Three-dimensional figure 3 demonstrates for $\beta=0.06$ with equal resource endowment of

countries A and B. This gives grounds to assume that optimization of the exchange rate dynamics is possible. Although, of course, the result will depend on time weighting.

Fig. 3. Optimization of the ruble exchange rate, resource balance. Source: developed by the authors.

The remaining figures show the simplest equilibrium integrals over time depending on the resource endowment of countries A and B, as well as on the beta parameter.

Figure 4 shows the theoretically most interesting situation of identical resource endowment of countries A and B for $\beta=0.06$. Analysis of the

figure allows us to conclude that for this situation the maximum relative income is provided by a small constant weakening of the ruble. This situation is more realistic for Russia – obvious resource superiority (in this specific example, 10 times). The optimal value of the currency parameter is slightly higher than for equal countries.

Fig. 4. Optimization of the ruble exchange rate, resource superiority. Source: developed by the authors.

Finally, Figure 5 shows the diametrically opposite situation of "resource insignificance" of country

A (in this specific example, less than 10 times than in country B).

Fig. 5. Optimization of the ruble exchange rate, resource insignificance. Source: developed by the authors.

In the model, the optimal exchange rate strategy also turns diametrically. In this situation, it seems appropriate to strengthen the ruble by 20-30%.

Figures 6 and 7 show the dependence of the optimization curves on the variations of the beta

parameter, which is equal to 0.05 and 0.07. We cannot know its value reliably for country A like Russia, which has a clear resource advantage over its competitor.

Fig. 6. Optimization of the ruble exchange rate. Resource superiority at beta=0.05. Source: developed by the authors.

Fig. 7. Optimization of the ruble exchange rate. Resource superiority at $\beta=0.07$.

Source: developed by the authors.

Conclusion

The following results were obtained as a result of the conducted research.

A two-country model of optimizing the national currency rate was constructed based on a two-industry approximation of the probabilistic market model. The theoretical and practical significance of this model is confirmed by the results obtained.

When constructing a two-country model for optimizing the national currency exchange rate, the following were chosen as the main factors:

- the level of weakening (strengthening) of the currency in relation to the equilibrium;
- the relative resource endowment of the country.

A series of digital experiments have been conducted, which have shown that for a country with above-average resource provision, it is advisable to weaken the national currency exchange rate within 30% of its equilibrium value. And vice versa - for a country with low resource provision, strengthening the national currency exchange rate is optimal.

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